

THE STRATEGIES OF SCIENTIFIC-TECHNICAL TRANSLATION FOR TEXTS

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Annotation: *We are living in an epoch in which science and technology are developing rapidly. Therefore, technical translation is playing an increasingly important part in the economic development and cultural prosperity of all nations. Newmark classifies different texts into three categories: expressive text, informative text, vocative text. Texts for science and technology belong to what we call a typical and distinctive informative type of texts. This paper explores the translation approaches and strategies applicable in texts of science and technology and then further explores the language, lexical and syntax features of texts for science and technology and discusses useful strategies for the translation of this type of text. In addition, a large number of sample translations of different types of technical texts, e.g. instructions, technical documents, etc. have been collected as data for discussions of the features and characteristics of typical technical texts. Finally, this thesis presents a number of methods and strategies for the translation of technical texts according to functional translation theory from a completely new perspective.*

Key Words: *Translation; Strategies; Science; Technology*

Nowadays science and technology are growing fast, new equipment is invented, new phenomena are discovered; consequently, new terms enter languages. As most western countries (and few eastern ones) are pioneers in the technology development, their languages are enriched with new vocabulary, among them, English, which is the international communication language, or lingua franca, has been receiving a wide range of scientific terms. Science did not always flow from the west to east but in the golden Islamic age Middle Ages was the scientific center of the world. The Arabic language was synonymous with learning and science for hundreds years; many scientific terms from Islamic communities were transferred to western languages such as, algebra, the names of the stars, Algorithm etc. Translation has a major role in the dissemination of science, and definitely this worldwide role for transfer of knowledge cannot be ignored. The translation impacts on science are unlimited; medicine, religious context, philosophy and astronomy and then chemistry were the earlier majors which were rendered (Wright, 1993). On the other hand the various levels of

technology development in countries can create major lexical gaps between source language (SL) and target language (TL), it can be said that the physical environment of a speech community is also involved in creating lexical gaps in the sense that words are made by speakers to refer to objects around us. However, globalization and the advent of the internet have increased translation pace; besides, the cultural and scientific concepts always transfer from high developed society to less developed society so that translators have to provide the languages with same equivalents. The term equivalent" refers to two or more entities being of equal value, corresponding value, or having same use or function as something else" (House, 2009), nevertheless sometimes they are pushed to borrow the exact words. A. Lexical Gap Lexical gaps are instances of lack of direct lexeme in one language while comparing two languages during translation. Bentivogli and Pianta (2000) underlined that a lexical gap occurs whenever a language expresses a concept with a lexical unit whereas another language expresses the same concept with a free combination of words, in other word, language is more flexible and all languages have capabilities to express any experience in corresponding terms. According to the dictionary of translation a lexical gap appears "if one word in one language does not have any counterpart in another language" which causes the translator to paraphrase source term. Lyons defined lexical gap as empty places in semantic fields where a language needs to compact some concepts, he also looked at lexical gaps through hierarchical lexical structures and believed lexical gaps are potential but non existing words Newmark classifies different texts into three categories: expressive text, informative text, vocative text. Texts for science and technology belong to what we call a typical and distinctive informative type of texts. The language of texts of science and technology is characterized by conciseness, accuracy, objectiveness, practicality, briefness and concreteness. It is therefore imperative that translators of this typology retain these characteristics when they reproduce them in the target language. Besides, the format of texts of science and technology is often standard, especially in technical texts. Even worse, a high proportion of such texts are poorly written and sometimes inaccurate, and it is usually the translator's job to "correct" their facts and their style. Meanwhile, the author's status in the text is anonymous, which adds to the difficulty of translation. Since proper translation of informative texts helps the learning of useful foreign technology and expertise worldwide and promotes China's technology development as a civilized country. There is no doubt that technical translation plays an extremely important role so further research should be made in order to enhance the translation quality of this typology. The Translation

Criterion for Texts of Science and Technology In technical translation, the main function is to inform the reader about technical information and phenomena in the real world. The choice of linguistic and stylistic forms is subordinate to this function. In a translation where both the source and the target texts are of the informative type, the translator should attempt to give a correct and complete representation of the source text's content and should be guided, in terms of stylistic choices, by the dominant norms of the target language and culture". Therefore, the translation of content-focused informative texts should be guided by the strategy of domestication and its relevant approaches informed by tenets of functional translation theory. Therefore, the first criterion is to ascertain whether their content and information is fully represented in the target language; Thus, once a given text is identified as belonging to the content-focused type, an important component of its translation method has been determined.

The criterion of judging the success of these texts is whether facts and contents are made clear to readers. No ambiguity is allowed, for there is only one fact. The second criterion for evaluating a content-focused text is the thoroughness of its orientation to the target language. Since a content-focused informative text is concerned with effective communication and accuracy of information and messages. That means expressing the same messages using the form of the target language as is shown in the following chart (figure 1). The content of source language should be transformed into target language content using target language forms. Therefore, content is more important than any other factors. Usually, for better understanding of texts for science and technology, translators change typically English grammar structure into Chinese structure, to better tell readers the fact that happens. Figure1. Transformation process from source text to target text Translation Strategies of Texts for Science and Technology Based on the linguistic feature and translation criterion of technical texts analyzed above, this following part of this paper will explore several methods and strategies for the translation of technical texts according to functional translation theory from a completely new perspective. Lexical Feature-Accuracy of Technical Terms. There are numerous professional terms in technical texts, and the texts are to convey scientific and technical content. So a translator must not only have a good command of language and translation competence, but know about science and technology. When translating, the translator must ensure the accuracy and trueness of the message in the translated text and carefully translate the technical terms so as to achieve the function of the translated text. To translate the terms specially used in certain fields, we must have some necessary knowledge of the

relevant fields. For this purpose, a translator has to keep in touch with the technical professionals to make clear the specific meaning of a technical word and to avoid being the laughing stock. The technical words fall in three categories: terms specially used in one field, terms derived from general words or terms that can be used in many fields, with different meaning in different fields, and lastly, acronyms.

Scientific and technical translation has always played a pivotal role in disseminating knowledge. Today, the domain of science and technology is the main area of translation work. Nevertheless, there is still a discrepancy between the growing need for high-quality technical translations and the short supply of competent technical translators to produce them, a situation which may be due in part to the recent neglect of the equivalence concept in the theoretical/descriptive and applied branches of translation studies (TS). This thesis sets out to redefine, reassess, and reinstate equivalence as a useful concept in TS by adopting an approach based on the English-German language pair and on one specific text genre and type. The investigation of equivalence as a qualitative complete-text-in-context-based concept is embedded in an equivalence-relevant methodology based on two methodological pillars, the first being a theoretically sound translation comparison and the second a highly refined translation corpus. Within this methodological framework, equivalence-relevant features are investigated and described at the syntactic, lexical-semantic, terminological-phraseological and overall textual levels. These levels are hierarchically interrelated in descending and ascending order and may be conditioned by pragmatic aspects, viz., domain knowledge and register considerations. The comparison is made using a high-quality corpus selected on the basis of a threefold set of selection criteria, with a special emphasis on the qualitative criteria. This helps us generate well-underpinned intersubjectifiable regularities in the form of potential equivalents established in the TT for ST equivalence-relevant features and enables us to obtain meaningful generalizations. Both regularities and generalizations should be capable of implementation in the applied branches of TS and, at the same time, help dynamize and intersubjectify the complex concept of equivalence. So, hopefully, this thesis will also contribute toward creating a link between the methodological, theoretical/descriptive and applied branches of TS to their mutual benefit. The impetus for an examination of the concept of equivalence in scientific and technical translation (STT) is both theoretically and practically motivated, since these two aspects are closely interrelated. The theoretical aspect addresses the low status of equivalence as a concept in translation studies (TS)

today, while the practical aspect involves the discrepancy between the growing need for high-quality technical translations and the short supply of competent technical translators to produce them (Schmitt 1985:37, Schmitt 1998a, BDU' Memorandum 19872), a situation which may itself be due in part to the recent neglect of the equivalence concept in the theoretical/descriptive and applied branches of TS.

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